

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of a Video-Assisted Teaching Program on Knowledge of Good Parenting Styles Among Mothers of Under-Five-Year-Old Children in the Pediatric Ward at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar).

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Most adults will become parents at some point in their lives, with around 89.6% of the adult population worldwide. Good parenting is crucial as it lays the foundation for a child's physical, emotional, and social development. It provides stability, security, and love, which are essential for healthy growth. While most strive to be great parents, many find themselves confused and frustrated by the seemingly endless challenges of parenthood. These challenges are evident across all developmental stages.

Objective: 1. To assess the level of knowledge regarding good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children.

2. To evaluate the effectiveness of a video-assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children.

3. To identify the association between the pre-test level of knowledge and selected demographic variables.

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How to Cite

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Method: A quasi-experimental (one-group pre-test post-test) design was adopted. A total of 35 women were selected as samples using a purposive sampling technique based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data collection and analysis were carried out in line with the study objectives.

Result: The results revealed that:

In the pre-test, the majority of mothers (27, 77.1%) belonged to the moderately adequate knowledge group, 3 mothers (8.6%) had adequate knowledge, and 5 mothers (14.3%) had inadequate knowledge about parenting styles.

In the post-test, 30 mothers (85.7%) shifted to the adequate knowledge category, 5 mothers (14.3%) remained in the moderately adequate group, and no one belonged to the inadequate knowledge group regarding good parenting styles.

Conclusion: The study concluded that interventional research should be conducted further to enhance knowledge about good parenting styles among mothers.

Keywords: Effectiveness, video-assisted teaching program, knowledge, practice, parenting style.

INTRODUCTION:

Parenting refers to the process of raising and nurturing children, encompassing the emotional, social, and physical support provided by caregivers. It involves guiding children's development, teaching values, and ensuring their well-being and education. Parenting encourages us to reflect on the kind of relationship we want with our child, our parenting priorities, and ways to avoid mistakes in upbringing that are often rooted in personal experiences and family life.

Most parents rely on their instincts or personal experiences when raising their children. While this can sometimes be helpful, it may not always lead to the best outcomes. When parents make mistakes in upbringing, it is not due to a lack of love but rather a lack of knowledge about more effective methods. Mistakes stemming from insufficient knowledge are often related to misleading or incomplete information, which can hinder effective parenting.

Research Problem Statement

"A study to assess the effectiveness of a video-assisted teaching program on knowledge of good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-

year-old children in the pediatric ward at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar)."

Objectives

1. To assess the level of knowledge regarding good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of the video-assisted teaching program on knowledge regarding good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children.
3. To find the association between the pre-test level of knowledge and selected demographic variables.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

1. **Assess:** Refers to the process of determining the knowledge of mothers of under-five-year-old children about good parenting styles.
2. **Effectiveness:** Refers to the degree to which the video-assisted teaching program achieves its intended results, measured in

terms of significant knowledge gained in the post-test.

3. **Video-Assisted Program:** Refers to a systematically developed and designed video on parenting styles.
4. **Knowledge:** Refers to the correct responses provided by mothers of under-five-year-old children regarding good parenting styles.

PARENTING STYLE: A parenting style is a pattern of behaviors, attitudes, and approaches that a parent uses when interacting with and raising their child.

HYPOTHESIS:

- **H1:** There will be a significant difference between the pre-test level of knowledge regarding parenting styles among mothers of under-5-year-old children.
- **H2:** There will be a significant association between the level of knowledge and video-assisted intervention regarding parenting styles among mothers of under-5-year-old children with their selected demographic variables.

ASSUMPTION: The study assumed that:

1. Mothers of under-5-year-old children have knowledge regarding parenting styles.
2. Videos will enhance the knowledge of mothers regarding parenting styles.
3. Mothers will attain more knowledge regarding parenting styles.

DELIMITATION: This study is delimited to:

1. The study will be conducted on mothers of under-5-year-old children in the pediatric ward of VPIMS, Lucknow, U.P.

2. The study is limited to 35 mothers of under-5-year-old children.

3. Participants willing to participate in the study.

RESEARCH APPROACH: The research approach used for this study was a quantitative research approach.

RESEARCH DESIGN: A quasi-experimental (one-group pre-test, post-test) design was adopted for this study.

VARIABLES: Variables are concepts at different levels of abstraction that are concisely defined to note their measurement or manipulation within the study.

Dependent Variables: The outcome or response due to the effect of independent variables, which the researcher wants to predict or explain.

"Knowledge level of good parenting style among mothers of under-five-year-old children in the pediatric ward."

Independent Variables: The stimulus or activity manipulated or varied by the researcher to create the effect on the dependent variable.

"Video-based teaching on good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children."

Demographic Variables: Characteristics and attributes of the study subjects considered as demographic variables:

- Age of the mother
- Educational level of the mother
- Number of children in the family
- Occupation of the mother
- Religion
- Type of family

- Previous knowledge regarding parenting

SETTING: The study was conducted in Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar).

POPULATION: The population consisted of mothers of under-five-year-old children in the pediatric ward at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar).

SAMPLE: A sample is a small portion of the population selected for observation and analysis. The sample for the study was mothers of under-five-year-old children in the pediatric ward at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar).

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: The purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample.

SAMPLE SIZE: The sample size of the study constituted 35 (n=35) mothers of under-five-year-old children who fulfilled the research criteria.

CRITERIA FOR SAMPLE SELECTION: The sample for the study was selected based on the following criteria:

- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Mothers of under-five-year-old children in the pediatric ward at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar).
 - Hindi was used as a medium for research.
- **Exclusion Criteria:**
 - Mothers of under-five-year-old children not present during data collection.
 - Mothers who are illiterate.

PILOT STUDY: The data from the self-structured knowledge questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. In the pilot study:

- Pre-test mean: 8.8 (SD = 1.72)
- Post-test mean: 14.4 (SD = 1.02)
- Paired t-test was used. The calculated t-value was 4.63, and the tabulated value for $df = 4$ was 0.004904 at a 0.05 level of significance.

The findings revealed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test means, demonstrating the study's feasibility.

RELIABILITY: The tool was tested for reliability by administering the self-structured knowledge questionnaire to five teachers with under-five-year-old children at Sudesh Multispeciality Hospital, Baadrabaad (Haridwar). The reliability was established using the split-half technique, resulting in a reliability score of 0.88, indicating high reliability.

RESULTS:

- **Section I:** Description of the sample according to their socio-demographic variables.
- **Section II:** Analysis of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores and the effectiveness of the video-assisted teaching program on good parenting styles among mothers of under-five-year-old children in the pediatric wards
- **Section III:** Association Between the Pre-Test Knowledge Score and Selected Demographic Variables

TableNo.4.1frequency and percentage distribution of sample according to their socio-demographic variables.

S.No	Socio-demographicAnalysisvariable	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Ageinyear	20-25Year	5	14.28%
		26-30Year	16	45.72%
		31-35Year	9	25.72%
		Above36year	5	14.28%
2	Religion	Hindu	30	85.79%
		Muslim	5	14.28%
		Christian	0	0%
		Other	0	0%
3	Educational qualification	primary	9	25.72%
		Secondary	2	5.72%
		10th& 12th	6	17.14%
		Graduate	18	51.42%
4	Occupation	Housewife	23	65.72%
		Government	1	2.85%
		Privatejob	10	28.58%
		Business	1	2.85%
5	Typeoffamily	Nuclear	23	65.72%
		Joint	12	34.28%
6	No .of children infamily	One	12	34.28%
		Two	14	40%
		Three	6	17.15%
		Above	3	8.57%

7	Source of previous knowledge regarding good parenting	Yes	8	22.85%
		No	27	77.15%
8	If yes source of information	Social media	6	75%
		Television	2	25%
		Newspaper	0	0%
		Family & friends	0	0%

SECTION-II

Analysis of Pre-Test and Post-Test Knowledge Scores and Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching on Knowledge of Good Parenting Style Among Mothers of Under-Five-Year-Old Children in the Pediatric Ward.

Table 4.2.1:

Percentage Distribution of Sample According to Pre-Test and Post-Test Knowledge Scores

This table presents the percentage distribution of mothers based on their knowledge scores in the pre-test and post-test. The analysis focuses on the existing levels of knowledge about good parenting styles before and after the intervention.

S.NO.	TEST	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE(%)
1.	PRE-TEST	INADEQUATE	5	14.3%
		MODERATELY ADEQUATE	27	77.1%
		ADEQUATE	3	8.6%
		TOTAL	35	100%
2.	POST-TEST LEVEL	INADEQUATE	0	0%
		MODERATELY ADEQUATE	5	14.3%
		ADEQUATE	30	85.7%
		TOTAL	35	100%

Fig. No 1.1 Analysis of Pre-Test and Post-Test Knowledge Scores and Effectiveness of Video-Assisted Teaching on Knowledge of Good Parenting Style Among Mothers of Under-Five-Year-Old Children in the Pediatric Ward

Table-4.2.3 The data were analyzed using the paired t-test to determine the significance of the difference between the pre-test and post-test knowledge scores. The findings are presented below:

PRE TEST SCORE	N	MEAN	S D	MEANDIFFERENCE	t-VALUE	p-VALUE
	35	7.9	1.42	3.9	-12.26	<0.0001 (significant)
POSTTEST SCORE	35	11.8	1.81			

- **t-value = -12.26 and p-value < 0.0001**
- The **mean post-test knowledge score** was **11.8**, and the **mean pre-test knowledge score** was **7.9**.

This indicates a statistically significant improvement in the knowledge scores of the women between the pre-test and post-test. The negative t-value suggests a reduction in error variance, and the p-value less than 0.05 (actually much less than 0.05) confirms that this change is highly significant and not due to random chance. Based on these results, **the research hypothesis (H1)** that there is a difference between the pre-test and post-test scores is **accepted**.

SECTION-III

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE PRE-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE AND THEIR SELECTED SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

In order to determine the association between the level of pre-test knowledge score and their selected demographic variables, the following hypothesis (H2) was formulated:

- **H2:** There is a significant association between the pre-test knowledge score and their selected demographic variables.

The data was analyzed using the chi-square test. The findings are presented in Table 4.3.1.

TableNo. 4.3.1

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES		PRETEST LEVEL						X ² VALUE (df)	p VALUE
		Inadequate n=5		Moderately adequate n=27		Adequate N=3			
		N	%	N	%	N	%		
AGE	20-25years	2	40%	3	11.1%	0	0%	4.88 (6)	0.559
	26-30years	2	40%	12	44.4%	2	66.7%		
	31-35years	1	20%	7	25.9%	1	33.3%		
	Above 30 years	0	0%	5	18.6%	0	0%		
RELIGION	HINDU	5	100%	22	81.5%	3	100%	1.728 (6)	0.942
	MUSLIM	0	0%	5	18.5%	0	0%		
	CHRISTIAN	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%		
	OTHER	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%		

Educational qualification	Primary	2	40%	7	25.9%	0	0%	5.243 (6)	0.513
	Secondary	0	0%	2	7.40%	0	0%		
	10 th and 12 th	0	0%	6	22.2%	0	0%		
	Graduate	3	60%	12	44.5%	3	100%		

	Andabove								
No. of children	One	1	20%	10	37%	1	33.3%	9.494 (6)	0.148
	Two	2	40%	10	37%	2	66.7%		
	Three	0	0%	6	22.3%	0	0%		
	Above	2	40%	1	3.70%	0	0%		
Type of family	Nuclear	0	0%	23	85.2%	0	0%	19.877 (2)	0.00004
	Joint	5	100%	4	14.8%	3	100%		
If yes Source of information	Social media	1	50%	4	80%	1	100%	1.067 (6)	0.982
	Television	1	50%	1	20%	0	0%		
	Newspaper	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%		
	Family and friends	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%		
Occupation of mother	Housewife	3	60%	20	74%	0	0%	15.38 (6)	0.017
	Government job	0	0%	1	3.70%	0	0%		
	Private job	2	40%	6	22.3%	2	66.7%		
	Business	0	0%	0	0%	1	33.3		
Any previous knowledge about good parenting style	Yes	2	40%	5	18.5%	1	33.3%	1.308 (2)	0.519
	No	3	60%	22	62.9%	2	66.7%		

Indicates a significant association:

The data presented in Table 4.3.1 shows that the chi-square test was used to determine the association between the pre-test knowledge score and the selected demographic variables. The findings of the chi-square test show that there was an association between the pre-test knowledge score and specific socio-demographic variables such as occupation, type of family, and good parenting style. In each case, the p-value was less than 0.05 (level of significance), hence the research hypothesis (H2) was accepted.

However, the chi-square test also showed that there was no association between the pre-test knowledge score and other socio-demographic variables such as age in years, religion, educational qualification, number of children in the family, any previous knowledge regarding good parenting style, and the source of previous knowledge.

RECOMMENDATIONS: Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

- This study can be conducted on a larger sample for better generalization of the research findings to a larger population.
- A comparative study can be carried out to ascertain the knowledge and attitude differences between different groups.

Conflict of Interest, Disclosures, Funding, and Consent:

1 Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

2 Disclosures:

The authors have no

additional disclosures to report.

3 Funding:

There is no funding provided by any organization or company for this study.

4 Consent:

Informed consent was obtained from all participants before inclusion in the study.

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